

Biochemical and molecular identification of sweet meat (Sandesh) spoiling bacteria

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Abstract : Sandesh is a very popular heat desiccated product of coagulated milk protein mass called chhana (a heat and acid coagulated product of milk, analogous to cottage cheese). This sweet meat can be easily affected by microorganisms during storage and consumption, which will cause sweet meat spoilage. The role of bacteria as a cause of spoilage of dairy products, like sweet meat, has been clearly demonstrated elsewhere. The aim of this study is to find out the microbes responsible for deterioration of the sweet meat (Sandesh). The study began with deteriorated Sandesh. It was spread on nutrient agar and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Two types of colonies were observed. One was white in color and the other was yellow. The organisms were identified according to the protocols followed by Bergey's Manual of systematic Bacteriology. Both the colonies were found to be Gram-positive and non-spore forming cocci. The bacteria were partially characterized through microscopic examination and by conventional biochemical tests. The identification of the organism was confirmed by 16s rRNA gene sequencing. It was found that the white colony was *Staphylococcus condimenti* and the yellow colony was *Staphylococcus gallinarum*.

Keywords : Sandesh, Gram-positive bacteria, 16s rDNA, phylogenetic analysis.

Introduction

Sandesh is one of the most popular and delicious sweet meat in India, especially in West Bengal¹. Its quality and shelf-life are very much dependent on the quantity of sugar and moisture content apart from freshness of the chhana and its processing technique.

Many dairy farms and milk processing industries have been developed in India². Since ancient times individual sweet makers called halwais are producing sweet meat. This profession needs hard labor and the quality of the production depends on its ingredients and the individual skill of the makers. But little attention is paid to the sanitary handling and packaging for extension of shelf life. Dairy products are susceptible to microbial growth as milk is an excellent source of nutrients like lactose, protein and fat. The organisms in dairy products release certain metabolites like lactic and organic acids, gases, enzymes, toxins etc. that affect the quality of the products and also render the products unsafe for consumption and storage.

Over recent years, the study of small subunits of ribosomal RNA has revolutionized the classification of microorganisms, both bacteria and fungi³. With the help of 16s rRNA analysis the identification of the bacteria responsible for the deterioration of sweet meat is confirmed.

To improve the microbiological quality of sweet meat (Sandesh), precaution must be taken at different critical control points⁴. Necessary steps should be taken by the sweet-makers for its long term preservation and safe consumption.

Although the details of the process, chemical composition and storage stability of Sandesh are available in literature^{5,6}, hardly anything is known about the microbiology of the products. The aim of this study is to identify the microbes responsible for sweet meat deterioration. If the growth of the microbes be arrested or the growth rate be minimized, the sweet meat can be stored safely. This is very much important for the consumers and manufacturers.

Materials and methods :

Development of indigenous cultures :

The Sandesh was collected from local market and kept at room temperature for deterioration. The cultures studied in this work were isolated from deteriorated sweet meat (Sandesh) sample. The Sandesh sample is diluted at the ratio of 1 : 10 (g/mL) in sterile distilled water. Serial dilutions were made in the ratio of 1 : 100, 1 : 1000 and 1 : 10000 in screw-capped test tube. Petri plates containing nutrient agar (Peptic digest of animal tissue-5 g/L, Beef extract-1.50 g/L, Yeast extract-1.50 g/L, Sodium chloride-5 g/L, Agar-15 g/L) were prepared. 1 ml of each dilution was poured separately on plates containing solid agar medium and then spread over the surface. Two plates were prepared for each dilution. These petri plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Developed colonies were picked up from the nutrient agar with sterile platinum loop. Sub-culturing was continued until pure culture was obtained. These pure colonies were transferred into the liquid media (Nutrient broth containing Peptic digest of animal tissue-5 g/L, Beef extract-1.5 g/L, Yeast extract-1.5 g/L, Sodium chloride-5 g/L) and growth was ascertained by the appearance of turbidity.

Preliminary characterization of isolated bacteria :

Characteristics of colonies viz. colour, shape etc. were recorded. Bacteria were categorized as Gram-positive or Gram-negative when they were respectively stained with crystal violet, counterstaining with safranin and observing under microscope. For spore staining, smear was floated with malachite green at moist heat for 10 min, washed with water and counterstained with safranin to observe the vegetative bacterial cells.

Purification and identification of culture :

For partial identification of bacterial culture, Voges Proskauer test, Methyl red test, Nitrate reduction test, Catalase test, Urease test, Starch hydrolysis and carbohydrate fermentation were carried out according to Bergey's Manual of determinative Bacteriology^{7,8} for characterization of bacterial cultures and further confirmation was done by 16s rRNA gene sequencing.

Genomic DNA extraction :

Genomic DNA from the two bacterial species were isolated using bacterial and genomic DNA extraction kit from HiMedia and the concentration of the isolated DNA

products was verified by visual examination of ethidium bromide-stained agarose gels as well as by spectrophotometrical analysis.

Amplification of 16s rDNA :

Partial amplification of the 16s rRNA gene was performed with the thermal cycler ABI 9700 (ABI, Foster City, USA). The PCR of the genomic DNA of two isolates were conducted in a final volume of 50 µL. The reaction mixture included 20–50 ng of isolated genomic DNA, 2U taq polymerase (Vivantis, India), 1x PCR buffer with 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200 µM each dNTP and 10 pM of each primer (Patel De Chem, India). The primers 515F (5'–3') GTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAA and 1492R (5'–3') TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT (primers purchased - Patel De Chem, India) were used to amplify a 875-bp fragment within the gene coding for the small ribosomal subunit (16s rRNA) of bacteria⁹. DNA was denatured for 2 min at 94 °C before amplification cycle and after amplification an extension step (7 min at 72 °C) was performed. The cycling parameters consisted of 28 cycles at : denaturation at 94 °C for 30 s, primer annealing at 45 °C for 1 min, extension at 72 °C for 1 min. The samples should be held at 4 °C until analysis by agarose gel electrophoresis is done. All the amplified PCR products were agarose-gel-eluted using HiMedia gel elution kit. The samples were sent for sequencing to Seq-India.

Accession number :

The sequences were submitted to Gene Bank and then accession numbers were assigned as : JF742781 for a.mb and JF742782 for y.mb.

Blast search in NCBI gene bank and phylogenetic analysis :

The partial 16s rDNA sequences of the isolated strains were compared with those available in the public databases. Identification to the species level was determined as a 16s rDNA sequence similarity of 100% and 99% with that of the prototype strain sequence in the Gene Bank. Using the BIOEDIT sequence editor and MEGA-4 software Phylogenetic tree was constructed.

Results

Isolation, characterization and biochemical identification of bacterial strains :

The identification and classification of bacteria are

primarily based on morphological and biochemical traits. In recent years, different molecular biology techniques have been developed for bacteria identification. In the present study, morphological, biochemical and a molecular approach (16s rRNA analysis) have been chosen to identify the bacteria responsible for sweet meat (Sandesh) spoilage.

The growth characteristics and the result of the different biochemical tests are given in Table 1. These results showed that both the isolated strains were Gram-positive and non spore forming cocci (cluster). One was white in color (a.mb) and the other was yellow (y.mb) in color. Moreover both the strains showed positive Catalase test and negative Voges Proskaur test. Methyl red, Nitrate reduction and Urease test results were negative for strain a.mb and positive for strain y.mb.

Table 1. Growth characteristics and biochemical test result

Parameters	Strain a.mb	Strain y.mb
Growth on nutrient agar plate	White, Irregular Star shaped	Yellow, Regular Circular
Morphological characters	Gram-positive and non spore forming cocci	Gram-positive and non spore forming cocci
Growth in nutrient broth	Turbid, growth	Turbid, growth
Voges-Proskaur test	-ve	-ve
Methyl-red test	-ve	+ve
Nitrate reduction test	-ve	+ve
Urease test	-ve	+ve
Starch hydrolysis test	Partially hydrolyzed	No hydrolysis
Catalase test	+ve	+ve
Glucose fermentation	-ve	-ve
Mannitol fermentation	-ve	-ve
Salicin fermentation	-ve	-ve
Sorbitol fermentation	-ve	-ve
Fructose fermentation	-ve	-ve
Raffinose fermentation	-ve	-ve
Dextrin fermentation	-ve	-ve

In Starch hydrolysis test it was observed that strain a.mb was partially hydrolyzed whereas no hydrolysis occurred in case of y.mb. Carbohydrate fermentation (Glucose, Mannitol, Salicin, Sorbitol, Fructose, Raffinose and Dextrin) tests showed similar result for the bacterial strains a.mb and y.mb. The entire carbohydrate fermentation tests were negative for a.mb and y.mb.

Phylogenetic analysis of 16s rRNA data :

Direct PCR amplification of 16s rRNA from a single isolate demonstrated excellent congruence between morphology and 16s rRNA sequence data. Each isolate was carefully characterized under the microscope and used for DNA amplification. Isolated strains were used for genomic DNA extraction followed by PCR amplification using 16s rRNA specific primers. All the PCR products were gel-purified and were partially sequenced to analyze their 16s rRNA genes.

The results were then analyzed using BLAST server at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). The sequence for each isolate was compared with Gene Bank reference sequences using the BLAST system (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). Sequence analysis of strain a.mb showed 100% and 99% similarity with 10 bacteria of Gene Bank. From this sequence analysis result, strain a.mb was identified as *Staphylococcus condimentii*. Sequence analysis of strain y.mb showed 100% and 99% similarity with 5 bacteria of Gene Bank and from this sequence analysis result, strain y.mb was identified as *Staphylococcus gallinarum*.

The selected 10 sequences for strain a.mb (*Staphylococcus condimentii*) were used to construct a Phylogenetic tree by neighbor joining method which was shown in Fig. 1.

Similarly selected 5 sequences for strain y.mb (*Staphylococcus gallinarum*) were used to construct a Phylogenetic tree by neighbor joining method which was shown in Fig. 2.

Discussion

In the present study two types of bacteria had been identified from the deteriorated Sandesh.

After gram staining it was found that both the bacteria were Gram-positive and non spore forming. According to Bergey's Manual of determinative Bacteriology Gram-positive cocci (cluster) shaped bacteria may be *Staphylococcus* sp., *Pedococcus* sp. or *Micrococcus* sp. All the isolates were initially screened by biochemical characterization, but routine biochemical tests were not sufficient for confirmation of their characterization.

To confirm the species 16s rRNA analysis was conducted. The results obtained from the analysis of the partial sequence of the two bacterial strains, isolated from deteriorated sweet meat, showed that they belong to the *Staphylococcus* gr. The isolates were identified as *Staphylococcus condimentii* and *Staphylococcus gallinarum*.

Fig. 1. Neighbor-joining tree based on distance analysis representing relationship between the 16s rRNA sequences a.mb bacterial isolates from sweet meat (Sandesh) sample.

Fig. 2. Neighbor-joining tree based on distance analysis representing relationship between the 16s rRNA sequences y.mb bacterial isolates from sweet meat (Sandesh) sample.

In the previous studies¹⁰ it was reported that *E. coli* had attracted much attention as an indicator organism for unhygienic condition during processing and production of sweet meats (Sandesh and Kalakand)¹⁰. But according to our observations it is for the first time that the species *Staphylococcus condimentii* and *Staphylococcus gallinarum* have been identified by 16s rRNA analysis in Indian sweet meat (Sandesh).

Staphylococcus species reside normally on the skin and mucosa of human beings¹¹. So it can be said that these bacterial strains grow in sweet meat due to a lack of hygienic measures at the time of manufacturing, handling and storage.

Further studies are going on to arrest the growth of these bacteria by adding natural food grade preservatives. If it is possible to prevent the growth and multiplication of bacteria in sweet meat (Sandesh) sample it will be very much effective for long term preservation and consumers' acceptance.

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